

protoclusters of galaxies: from Planck to the Euclid and JWST era

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protoclusters of galaxies: from Planck to the Euclid and JWST era

- Planck Collab, XXVII, 2015 – arXiv:1503.08773 – our Herschel / Planck study
- Flores-Cacho et al, 2015 – arXiv:1510.01585 – one of our structures
- Planck Collab, XXXIX, 2016 – arXiv:1508.04171 – the whole Planck sample
- McKenzie et al., 2017 – arXiv:1703.02074 – the SCUBA2 view
- Martinache et al., 2018 – arXiv:1810.07330 – the Spitzer view
- Kneissl et al., 2019 – arXiv:1804.06581 – ALMA view of one structure

+ Thibaut Perdereau (PhD), Clément Martinache, Mari Poletta, Matt Lehnert, Brenda Frye, Geneviève Soucail, Helmut Dannerbauer, Alessandro Rettura et al.

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star formation in high- z clusters

CSFRD

Protoclusters occupy a cosmic volume of at most 5% at $z < 7$.

At $z > 2$ they account for 20-50% of the total SFR.

Chiang et al., 2017

protoclusters, clusters: formation

Schimakawa et al., 2018
arXiv:1809.08755

	Declining Phase	Maturing Phase	Growing Phase
Galaxies	Starvation / Environmental quenching	Energetic AGN feedback	Massive galaxy formation
Halo Gas	Cold gas depletion / Superheated plasma	Pre-heating / Core collapse	Cold gas stream in hot gas

But how to explain the coexistence at $z \sim 2$ or $z \sim 2.5$ of X-Rays (proto)clusters vs SF protoclusters at the same time ?

Chiang et al., 2017
arXiv:1705.01634

low-z, high-z clusters ? Protoclusters ?

Overzier, 2016

adapted from Dekel & Birnboim, 2006

low-z, high-z clusters ? Protoclusters ?

Behroozi+ 2019

low-z, high-z clusters ? Protoclusters ?

Behroozi+ 2019

few examples of famous (proto)clusters

Wang et al., 2016 $z=2.5$

Mei et al., 2015 $z=1.9$

Oteo et al., 2018 $z=4.0$

Noirot et al., 2018 $z < 2.8$

Dannerbauer et al., 2017
Emonts et al., 2018 $z=2.16$

Miller et al., 2018 $z=4.3$

Gobat et al., 2011 $z=2.07$

Umehata et al., 2019 $z=3.1$

Mantz et al., 2014 $z=1.9$

Noirot et al., 2011 z=2.8

et al., 2018 z=4.002

Flores-Cacho et al., 2014 z=2.095

Strazzullo et al., 2014 z=2.0

Mei et al., 2014 z=2.0

Brodwin et al., 2014 z=2.508

Rettura et al., 2014 z=2.0

Wang et al., 2014 z=2.0

Iverson et al., 2014 z=2.0

Hatch et al., 2014 z=2.0

Santos et al., 2011, z=1.58

Fassbender et al., 2014 z=1.58

Daddi et al., 2009 z=4.05

Privantz et al., 2014 z=1.58

Venemans et al., 2014 z=2-3

Kodama et al., 2007 z=2-3

I. Lemaux et al., 2014 z=3

Selection function !

Impacts on planes that came back (illustration)

story of Abraham
Wald in WWII
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Survivorship_bias

5
02
1.75
8-2.3
=2.0
z=5.3
z=1.62

z > 2

z = 2-3

2. Extragalactic Background Light SED

CIB > COB

CIB peaks at ~200μm or 1500 GHz

EBL ~ 5% of CMB

2. high-SFR high-z clusters: Planck+Herschel

→ Herschel and Planck proto-cluster candidates

Planck selection:

Cold spots of the CIB

Color selection

Thèse: David Guéry

Planck Collab., 2015, Int XXVII, arXiv:1503.08773 – Herschel study
Planck Collab., 2016, Int XXXIX, arXiv:1508.04171 – Planck sample
Press Releases: ESA, NASA, INSU, A&A

2. from Planck to Herschel to Spitzer

Planck / HFI – 2151 candidates (FIR/mm)

Planck int. results XXXIX, Planck collab., 2016

Herschel / SPIRE – 228 observed (FIR ↔ dust) 98% success

Planck int. results XXVII, Planck collab., 2015

Spitzer / IRAC – 82 observed (NIR ↔ stellar component)

Martinache et al., 2018

Courtesy Benjamin Clarenc

Martinache et al., 2018 arXiv:1810.07330

3. the case of one field: Herschel & Spitzer

Herschel-SPIRE
3-color image:
blue = 250um
green = 350um
red = 500um

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Euclid will provide this kind of sensitivity over the whole sky !
 JWST can follow-up exquisitely !

Martinache, et al., 2018

3. the case of one field: Herschel & Spitzer

Thesis of Thibaut Perdereau

Martinache, et al., 2018

$\Delta\alpha_{2000}$

3. the case of one field: Herschel & Spitzer

Martinache, et al., 2018

3. and we have a few fields

Herschel-SPIRE
3-color image:
blue = 250um
green = 350um
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Planck Collab., 2015, Int XXVII, arXiv:1506.01962

3. and we have a few fields

Herschel-SPIRE
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**star
formation**

Planck Collab., 2015, Int XXVII

4.1 what do we learn from imaging ? SFR

Huge SFR

-> unique sample selected by extreme SFR over the whole sky

SPHerIC:
Spitzer Planck Herschel Infrared Clusters

Planck 2015, Martinache et al., 2018

4.2 what do we learn from imaging ? Overdensities

Martinache et al., 2018

5. SFR vs z: samples

6. cross-correlations

Hurier et al., in prep

6. LOFAR helps ! LoTSS

Thanks to 1st year students of Univ. Paris-Sud: Elise Lagarde, Tassadit Rebrab, Marguerite Boscq, Pierre Nonnon

7. how Euclid can help: stellar component

2 main scientific goals:

- Dark matter
- Dark energy

And lots of « legacy science »

4 bands: VIS, Y, J, H.

Launch: 2022.

7. Euclid great potential

Wang+16
z=2.5 cluster

=> Euclid
data will be
full of those
clusters !

+ ground
based
surveys,
LSST

Louis Legrand, Clément Martinache, Benjamin Clarenc, T. Etourneau, H. Dole

8. great prospects w/ JWST

Feasibility demonstrated during the ERS phase.
 B. Frye, H. Dole, et al.

9. conclusions, perspectives

→ Herschel and Planck protoclusters

Planck
Planck

- Protonclusters are important:
 - Significant contribution to the SFR at $z > 2$
 - Structure formation, dark matter and baryons
 - Fate of the gas ?
 - Various ways to select them
- Planck SPHerIC sample: 100s of extreme structures selected over the whole sky, extreme SFR, $z > 1.5$
- Nicely complements other selections
- JWST and Euclid will help
- [So other facilities: SZ, X, mm, IR, ...]
- Towards a coherent view on the patchy landscape of protonclusters

... et al., in prep

